

Syndications in Islamic and Conventional Banking: Mapping Research Topics Using VOSviewer Bibliometric and Literature Review

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the development of research around Syndicate in Islamic and Conventional. The research was conducted from 2011 to 2022, by searching national journals indexed by Sinta via the Garuda website, with the keyword "Syndicate". Based on the search results, there were 41 research articles, then inputted into the VOSviewer application and analyzed descriptively through a literature review study. The results showed that the number of publications had increased significantly every year. Furthermore, based on the results detected using the VOSviewer application, research related to Syndicate is divided into 9 clusters and 140 items. Meanwhile, based on the results of a literature review study, there are 17 main themes related to Syndicates in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

Keywords: Syndicate, Bibliometrics, VOSviewer, Literature Review, Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

INTRODUCTION

Development of the economic sector, especially in Islamic and Conventional Sharia Financial Institutions (financial market sharia) is experiencing an increasing trend, especially in several countries where the majority of the population is Muslim, including Indonesia. The sharia financial market itself continues to experience development, namely in the financing sector, capital markets, sharia cooperatives and sharia finance. In its development, economic actors need easy and reliable financing. Therefore, a financing model is needed that includes cooperation from several financing providers such as banks and other institutions. The appropriate financing in this case is syndicated credit financing.

In previous research, when linked to Islamic and Conventional Sharia Financial Institutions, Syndicated credit was considered the right choice for economic actors because the Syndicated model of credit financing can provide convenience in very large loans for economic actors. Syndicated Credit is a credit provided by two or more Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions or banks with terms and conditions that are in accordance with the applicable agreement. The development of credit syndication in conventional banking is also quite rapid. This is in line with the development of the banking industry as a whole. In 2020, there were several credit syndication transactions involving conventional banking, including a credit syndication worth IDR 5.5 trillion for PT PLN (Persero) in February 2020 and a credit syndication worth IDR 7.2 trillion for PT Adaro Energy Tbk in May 2020. Apart from that, several conventional banks such as Bank Mandiri, Bank BRI, and Bank CIMB Niaga are also involved in interbank credit syndicated transactions. The development of credit syndication in sharia banking in Indonesia has been quite rapid in recent years. This is in line with the growing growth of the sharia banking industry. In 2020, there were several credit syndication transactions involving sharia banking, including a credit syndication worth IDR 2.2 trillion for PT Baturona Adimulya in May 2020 and a credit syndication worth IDR 4.85 trillion for PT Pengerukan Indonesia Raya in August 2020. Apart from Additionally, there are also several sharia banks involved in interbank credit syndicated transactions, such as Bank Mandiri Syariah, Bank Muamalat, and Bank BNI Syariah.

Previous research regarding Syndication itself has experienced an increase over time. This can be proven by the existence of 37 studies on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) from 2013 to 2022. Several journals have also discussed syndication, both conventional and sharia. This is proof that syndicated financing will continue to exist and be applied over time. The aim of this research is to map the development of research and publication of scientific articles related to Syndication in various Islamic and Conventional Sharia Financial Institutions over the period of their development using bibliometric research methods. VOSviewer and also literature review studies.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Syndicated credit is the provision of credit by two or more banks to a debtor to finance a project with the same conditions as a general credit agreement. The agreement is jointly signed and managed by an agent (appointed bank). This financing is written in one credit agreement document between the debtor and all banks involved in the syndication, and this document becomes the guide for all syndication participants. Syndicated financing is basically a convenience in helping to obtain large amounts of financing for the company's cash finances. Syndication is also considered very helpful for borrowers because borrowers can apply for financing from more than one bank. According to Law no. 10 of 1998 concerning sharia syndicated financing, provides funding based on an agreement made by both parties involved in determining the agreed repayment period and profit sharing at a later date.

Bibliometric analysis is a process that carries out scientific bibliographic studies and analysis, which assumes that a researcher who is observing the object of his research must monograph the results of the research observations with his colleagues. This will provide information about the progress of the research carried out. VOSviewer is a computer programming technique that provides convenience in visualizing and sharing bibliometric knowledge for free. VOSviewer is a tool that helps in bibliometrics to visualize such relationships. The relationship in question can be in the form of previous sources in the form of journals or results that have been published by a previous researcher.

Literature Review is a scientific research method that aims to describe the development of a particular object. Through a " literature review ", researchers can analyze existing theories or methods, or develop new theories or methods that are appropriate to the research object. This method is often used to find new theories that can be used in research.

METHODOLOGY

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in literature review studies. The object of the research is Syndication in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Syndication originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Syndication " for the entire year (2011 -2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) map topics, methods, research findings, and research gaps based on literature review studies.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Syndication in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

The results of searches for scientific publications regarding syndication in Islamic and Conventional Sharia Financial Institutions from 2013 to 2022 show an increase in publications, especially in 2018 and 2019 which reached 7 articles. However, in 2020 the publication of these articles decreased so that there were only 5 articles. Even in 2021 and 2022, searches for syndicated articles continue to decline. This shows that there is still minimal research on syndication, and this shows that the publication of syndicated articles is unpredictable every year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Syndication by year

Year	Number of Articles	Year	Number of Articles
2011	2	2018	7
2013	2	2019	7

2015	1	2020	5
2016	3	2021	3
2017	6	2022	5
Total 41			

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, you can find 22 affiliates/institutions that publish research articles regarding syndication in Islamic and Conventional Sharia Financial Institutions. Lex Et Societatis is the largest journal publishing institution, with 3 articles.

Table 2. Affiliates/institutions publishing scientific publications regarding syndication

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Lex Et Societatis	3
Kertha Wicara: Legal Science Journal, Collection of Law Faculty Student Journals	2
MEA Scientific Journal, Journal of Sharia and Legal Studies, Bulletin of Monetary Economics and Banking, Diponegoro Law Journal, Indonesian Notary, Research Journal of Sharia Economic Law and Islamic Culture, ADIL Journal, At-Tamwil Journal: Sharia Economic Studies, Bina Mulia Hukum Journal, Bonum Commune Business Law Journal, Ius Quia Iustum Legal Journal, Ius Quia Iustum Legal Journal, MEA Scientific Journal (Management, Economics, & Accounting), Journal of Accounting and Sharia Business (AKSY), Kertha Semaya: Journal of Legal Science, Legal Opinion, LEX CRIMEN, LEX PRIVATUM, MLJ Merdeka Law Journal, JURNAL OF SHARIA BANKING, AL-MASHARIF: JURNAL OF SCIENCE ECONOMICS AND ISLAMIC, Recital Review, Sultan Agung Notary Law Review, Syntax Literate, to-ra	1

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Furthermore, all researchers only wrote 1 journal article about syndication in Islamic and Conventional Sharia Financial Institutions. They are Ika Novitasari, Noor Ifada, Husni, Rahmady Liyantanto, T. Murwadi, AA Mirah Endraswati, I Ketut Sudantra, Meyske Fransiska Harmain, Dian Bagus Pratama, Budiharto, Sartika Nanda, Sri Mulyani, Felix Andreas Sutanto, Heribertus Yulianton, Stivenly Christian Sumual, I Gusti Ngurah Krisna Aditya Putra, I Nyoman Darmadha, Lidya Nathalia, Mardiana Yose, Rully Trihantana, Mohamad Kharis Umardani, Pranindita Ayuningtyas, Grandaldo Yonanes Tindangen, Bernard Renaldy Suteja, Ety Mulyati, Lastuti Abubakar, Huriyah Raih Cita, AA Sagung Wira Chantieka, Ibrahim R, Nurfitriani, Eko Tama Putra Saratian, Alugoro Mulyowahyudi, Augustina Kurniasih, Astin Agus Yado, Kartika Dyah Angraeni, Krisnadi Nasution, Rahmayati, Ardany Zulfiqar, Lalu Husni, Lalu Wira Pria Suhartana, Aristo Djaman, Handriyanto Wijaya, Vivi Sylvia Purborini, Mohammad Gufon, Diah Aju Wisnuwardhani, Nabila Satira Harahap, Nicko Priady, Dery Ariswanto, Zedra Warang, Agung Wildan Azizi, Gilang Samudra, Gina Sakinah, Nurhaeti Nurhaeti, Taufiq Ridwan Murtadho, Jamaluddin, Nurul Islami, and Jordhy Rizaldo.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research Regarding Syndication in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

When searching the results on the Garuda website, there are 41 research articles regarding Syndication in Islamic and Conventional Sharia Financial Institutions in Indonesia. After that, the article is downloaded in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then input and interpreted using the VOSviewer device and obtained the following results:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding Syndication in Islamic and Conventional Sharia Financial Institutions

Data source: Processed data, VOSviewer 1.6.18 software.

co-word map network visualization regarding the development of research regarding Syndication in Islamic and Conventional Sharia Financial Institutions are divided into 9 clusters with 140 topics, as in Figure 1 are as follows:

- Cluster 1. Red covers 27 topics, namely: bank, LLL, CD instrument, contract, conventional financial institution, credit derivative, credit risk, debtor, development, document, field, fixed collateral, formulation, fund, implementation, international syndication loan, Islamic financial institution, keyword, large amount, loan, obligation, order, perspective, right, syndicated loan, third, violation.
- Cluster 2. Green covers 20 topics, namely: at tamwil al mashrifi al mujam, bank dki, sharia bank legal perspective, sharia bank credit agreement, project, sharia, usd.
- Cluster 3. Blue covers 19 topics, namely: bank aceh syariah, characteristic, data, descriptive study, event, explanatory survey, financial data, financing, financing portfolio, financing product, islamic bank, nature, project, pt bank aceh syariah, research, method, risk, study, symptom, syndicated financing.
- Cluster 4. Yellow covers 19 topics, namely: agent, agreement, approach, attorney, authentic deed, credit document, institution, legislation, notary, position, power, procedure, relationship, research, responsibility, role, syndicated loan, syndicated loan agreement, syndicated loan participant.
- Cluster 5. Purple color covers 19 topics, namely: agree, maximum limit for granting participant credit, cassie, consent, credit, hsbc, http, k pdt, legal lending limit, legal relations, loan transfer, new creditor, org, pdgt, diversion receivables, pesertum, pnclp, syndicated credit agreement, verdict.
- Cluster 6. Blue covers 11 topics, namely: applicability, case, domain, enterprise, flexible polypeptide, innovation input, investment, number, peptide, time, venture capital.
- Cluster 7. Orange covers 10 topics, namely: banking company, legal standing, non-bank financial services institution, limitation, ijknb, non-bank finance, provision, regulator, sebi, syndicated credit.
- Cluster 8. The color brown covers 8 topics, namely: credit agreement, creditor, crediture againts, faculty agent bank, creditor, llm, redemption, credit rescue action.
- Cluster 9. The color pink covers 7 topics, namely: agent, credit syndication agent, paragraph, relating to debt, simple proof, bankruptcy applicant, uuk.

Mapping Literature Review regarding Problems in Credit Syndication in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Based on a literature review study in research journals that have been downloaded, there are 17 problems in Credit Syndication in Islamic and Conventional Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions, namely:

First, creditor bankruptcy in credit syndication. Settlement of creditor bankruptcy in a credit syndication can be carried out through several steps, including: (1) Formation of a Bankruptcy Resolution Team. The credit syndicate must form a bankruptcy resolution team consisting of legal experts, accountants and other creditor representatives. This team will be responsible for evaluating the financial situation of companies experiencing financial problems and determining the appropriate bankruptcy resolution strategy. (2) Negotiations with Main Creditors. Credit syndicators must negotiate with the main creditors of companies experiencing financial problems to find the most appropriate

bankruptcy resolution solution. These main creditors will usually have higher rights in decision-making, so it is important for credit syndicators to ensure that their interests are fairly represented. (3) Negotiations with Other Creditors. The credit syndicate must also negotiate with other creditors involved in the credit syndication. It is important to ensure that the bankruptcy settlement agreement covers all parties involved in the credit syndication. (4) Agreement Evaluation. Once a bankruptcy settlement agreement is reached, the bankruptcy resolution team must evaluate the agreement to ensure that it is fair to all parties involved. This evaluation should consider all aspects of the deal, including debt payments, transfer of assets, and interest payments. (5) Implementation of the Agreement. Once the agreement is evaluated and approved by all parties involved, the credit syndicate must implement the agreement. This includes paying off debts, transferring assets, and paying interest in accordance with the agreed agreement. (6) Monitoring Company Conditions. Once the bankruptcy settlement agreement is executed, the credit syndicate must monitor the company's financial condition to ensure that the company can meet its financial obligations and continue to operate effectively. This monitoring will also help identify potential future financial risks and ensure that the credit syndicate is prepared to address any financial problems that may arise.

Second, banking syndication financing is based on conventional law, contract law, DSN-MUI fatwa no. 19/2014, and Sharia Economic Law/HES, namely:

- Syndicated financing in banking is regulated by several laws and regulations, including: (1) Law Number 10 of 1998 concerning Banking, which regulates banking activities, including syndicated financing. In this law, it is regulated that banks can carry out joint financing with other banks through syndication. (2) Bank Indonesia Regulation Number 13/1/PBI/2011 concerning the Implementation of Commercial Bank Business Activities, which provides guidelines to commercial banks in carrying out their business activities, including syndicated financing. (3) Bank Indonesia Regulation Number 16/18/PBI/2014 concerning the Implementation of Commercial Bank Governance Principles, which regulates banking governance, including syndicated financing, to ensure that bank activities are carried out in a transparent, accountable and professional manner. (4) Bank Indonesia Regulation Number 17/3/PBI/2015 concerning Reporting Activities and Other Reporting Obligations, which regulates bank reporting obligations in their business activities, including syndicated financing. Apart from that, syndicated financing in banking must also comply with other regulations and laws, such as business competition law, capital market law and tax-related regulations.
- In Islamic law, syndicated financing is also known as *mudharabah mutlaqah*. Basically, syndicated financing in Islamic law must comply with sharia principles, namely: (1) Principle of Certainty: Syndicated financing must produce certainty regarding the rights and obligations of each party involved, including certainty regarding the distribution of profits and losses. (2) Principle of Justice: Syndication financing must be fair for all parties involved, including a clear agreement regarding the distribution of profits and losses. (3) Principle of Social Responsibility: Syndicated financing must pay attention to the social impact of the project or business being financed. (4) Principle of Transparency: Syndicated financing must be transparent and follow applicable regulations. In syndicated financing, a bank or financial institution will become a joint owner of the project or business being financed, and the asset owner will entrust the management and management of the business to one of the banks or financial institutions involved in the syndication. Profit sharing in syndicated financing must be agreed in advance by all parties involved, and must be based on a fair and transparent agreement. Profit sharing must follow sharia principles, where banks or financial institutions that provide financing can only receive profits in the form of profit sharing, not interest. In the event of a loss, the bank or financial institution providing financing must bear responsibility in accordance with the proportion of financing provided by each party involved in the syndication.
- DSN-MUI Fatwa No. 32/DSN-MUI/X/2002 concerning Syndicated Financing in Banking explains the syndicated financing mechanism applied in sharia banking. The following are several important points from the fatwa: (1) Syndicated financing is a form of cooperation between two or more sharia banks to finance a project or business activity by dividing risks and profits proportionally; (2) Banks involved in syndicated financing must have a clear cooperation agreement regarding the rights and obligations of each party, including the sharing of risks and profits; (3) Syndicated financing can be carried out in the form of *mudharabah*, *musyarakah*, or a combination of both, in accordance with sharia principles; (4) In syndicated

financing, the bank as the owner of the funds must obtain sufficient information regarding the project or business activity to be financed, including potential risks and profits; (5) Syndicated financing can be carried out for projects or business activities that are halal and can provide benefits to the community; (6) Banks involved in syndicated financing must ensure that the projects or business activities financed comply with sharia principles and do not violate applicable provisions; (7) Profit sharing in syndicated financing must be proportional to the size of each bank's participation; (8) Banks involved in syndicated financing must obtain permission from customers to disclose information regarding projects or business activities financed to other banks involved in syndicated financing; and (9) Syndicated financing must not use interest mechanisms (riba) and must not violate other sharia principles. This fatwa provides clear guidelines and rules regarding syndicated financing in banking from an Islamic sharia perspective.

Third, collateral in the syndicated credit agreement through a Letter of Undertaking/LoU. LoU is a written statement issued by the bank as a guarantee or promise of payment on behalf of the borrower to a third party related to a syndicated credit agreement. LoU provides a guarantee that the bank will pay a third party on behalf of the borrower if the borrower fails to fulfill its obligations in accordance with the credit agreement. LoUs are usually used in international transactions or interbank transactions involving third parties, such as payments for imports or exports of goods or services. In a syndicated credit agreement, the LoU can be used to provide a guarantee to syndicated participants that the lending bank will fulfill its obligation to pay interest and principal on time. In practice, LoUs can also be used as collateral for banks participating in syndicated credit agreements, so that banks can minimize the credit risk taken in these agreements. However, it is important to remember that the use of LoUs must be done carefully, because there is a risk of misuse or fraud by irresponsible parties. Ultimately, the collateral in a syndicated credit agreement via LoU will depend on the terms and conditions stipulated in the credit agreement. Therefore, it is very important for the parties involved in a syndicated credit agreement to properly understand the contents and implications of each provision related to the collateral provided through the LoU.

Fourth, syndicated credit as an alternative to large-scale credit financing. Syndicated credit is a form of financing that involves several banks or financial institutions in providing loans to borrowers who need funds on a large scale. This loan is provided on the condition that each bank or financial institution involved in the syndication provides a share of the total loan in accordance with a predetermined agreement. The following are some of the advantages and benefits of syndicated credit as an alternative to large-scale credit financing: (1) Large financing: Syndicated credit usually provides large-scale financing which is difficult to obtain through single financing from one bank or financial institution. (2) Risk diversification: Syndicated credit helps diversify risks between several banks or financial institutions involved, so that each bank or financial institution is less exposed to a single credit risk. (3) Ease of arrangement: Syndicated credit is usually easier to arrange than looking for several banks or financial institutions separately, because the agreement made can include the same terms for all parties involved. (4) Flexibility in term and interest rates: Syndicated credit can be tailored to the borrower's needs, including more flexible terms and interest rates. (5) Faster settlement: Syndicated loans are usually quicker to settle than looking for several banks or financial institutions separately. However, as an alternative to large-scale credit financing, syndicated credit also has several disadvantages, such as higher costs compared to single loans, as well as more complicated documentation and legal requirements because it involves several banks or financial institutions. Therefore, it is important for borrowers to carefully consider the benefits and risks before deciding to use syndicated credit as an alternative to large-scale credit financing.

Fifth, material collateral becomes cash collateral in international syndicated credit guarantees. The process for converting material collateral into cash collateral in international syndicated credit guarantees can be carried out through the following steps: (1) Evaluation of Material Collateral. First of all, the bank or financial institution that provides syndicated credit will evaluate the material collateral provided by the borrower. If the material collateral has sufficient value to guarantee credit, the bank will consider accepting the collateral as cash collateral. (2) Assessment of Collateral Value. Next, the bank will assess the value of the material collateral and determine the amount of cash equivalent to the value of the collateral. (3) Agreement. The bank and borrower will then make an agreement to convert the material collateral into cash collateral. This agreement will determine the amount of cash that will be provided as collateral and other conditions related to cash collateral. (3)

Implementation. After the agreement is made, the borrower will provide material collateral to the bank or financial institution that provides credit, and the bank will provide an amount of cash equivalent to the value of the material collateral. (4) Credit Repayment. If the borrower succeeds in paying the credit according to the agreed time period, the cash collateral will be returned to the borrower. However, if the borrower fails to pay the credit, the bank will use the cash collateral to pay the outstanding credit.

Sixth, resolving bad debts in syndication. Settlement of bad debts in a syndication usually involves several parties, such as the bank as the main lender, other syndicate participating banks, asset managers, and borrowers. The following are several ways that can be done to resolve bad debts in syndication: (1) Renegotiation of Credit Agreements. One way to resolve bad credit is to renegotiate credit agreements. Renegotiations may include credit restructuring, payment delays, reduced interest rates, or reduced loan amounts. The goal is to provide financial relief to borrowers so they can repay the credit. (2) Asset Sales. Lenders may try to resolve bad debts by selling assets pledged as collateral by the borrower. Asset stewards can assist in this process by evaluating the asset's value and assisting with marketing. (3) Payment Negotiation. Lenders can negotiate with borrowers to find a way out of bad credit. They may offer options such as lower installment payments or longer repayment terms. (4) Refinancing. Refinancing is another option that can be done to resolve bad credit. This involves buying back the debt by a bank or other syndicate participant at a discount and replacing the debt with a new, better loan. (5) Asset Expropriation. The lender can take over the borrower's assets and sell them to pay back the debt. However, this may be difficult to do depending on the type of asset and applicable regulations.

Seventh, the role of the notary in syndication. Notaries can play an important role in syndication, especially in the process of forming syndication agreements. Syndication is a form of cooperation between several parties to provide large amounts of funding for a particular project or transaction. In this case, a notary can help in the following matters: (1) Making a syndication agreement: A notary can help in making a syndication agreement between all parties involved. This agreement will contain the terms and conditions of cooperation, including how to share risks, responsibilities and profits. (2) Providing certification and legality: The notary can provide certification that the syndication agreement has been made and agreed to by all parties involved. This gives legality and legal force to the agreement. (3) Ensure legal compliance: The notary can also ensure that the syndication agreement complies with all applicable legal requirements. This will help prevent legal problems in the future. (4) Storing agreement documents: Notaries can store syndication agreement documents safely, so that they can be accessed and used in the future if necessary.

Eighth, legal protection for the parties in the syndicated credit agreement. Legal protection in a syndicated credit agreement is aimed at protecting the interests of all parties involved, namely the lender (syndicated bank) and the borrower (usually a large company). The following are several legal protections that can be provided in a syndicated credit agreement: (1) Syndicated Credit Agreement. The main legal protection in a syndicated credit agreement is the agreement itself. Syndicated credit agreements must be made clearly and firmly, so that all parties understand their rights and obligations. The agreement must include provisions regarding the loan amount, interest, term, as well as the rights and obligations of each party. (2) Guarantee. Lenders usually require collateral from borrowers in the form of assets or personal guarantees, to guarantee that the loan will be repaid. These guarantees can include mortgages on land and buildings, mortgages on vehicles, and personal guarantees from major shareholders or directors of the company. This guarantee provides legal protection to the lender if the borrower cannot repay the loan. (3) Applicable Law. The syndicated credit agreement must state the applicable law in the agreement. This is important because each country has different rules and regulations related to credit and loans. By determining the applicable law, all parties can know their rights and obligations clearly and definitely. (4) Sanctions. The syndicated credit agreement must also include sanctions or consequences that will be given if one party violates the terms of the agreement. These sanctions may include fines or higher interest, or even termination of the credit relationship. With this sanction, all parties will be more careful in implementing the agreement. (5) Arbitration. Syndicated credit agreements may include provisions regarding dispute resolution through arbitration. Arbitration is a dispute resolution process outside of court, where the dispute is resolved by a neutral third party. Arbitration can be faster and cheaper than going through court, so it can provide more effective legal protection for all parties.

Ninth, the responsibility of the syndicated credit agent when a debtor defaults. As a syndicated credit agent, your responsibilities depend on the syndication agreement that has been agreed between

all parties involved, including the lending bank, debtor, and members of the credit syndicate. However, in general, as a syndicated credit agent, you are responsible for coordinating and facilitating communications and actions between all parties involved in the syndication. When a debtor defaults, then as a syndicated credit agent, your responsibilities are as follows: (1) Follow up: You need to immediately follow up on the debtor's default problem by collecting the latest information about the debtor's financial situation and considering the options available to resolve the problem. (2) Coordinating: You must also coordinate with all related parties in the syndicate to determine the steps that must be taken to resolve the problem. This may involve requesting additional information from the debtor, developing an action plan to restore credit, or filing a lawsuit against the debtor if necessary. (3) Monitoring: You must also continue to monitor the situation and ensure that all relevant parties in the syndication continue to communicate and work together to resolve the problem. (4) Providing Reports: You must provide regular reports to all related parties in the syndicate regarding the development of the situation and the actions that have been taken to resolve the debtor's default problem.

Tenth, syndicated financing to increase the financing portfolio. Syndicated financing can be an effective way to increase your financing portfolio. Syndicated financing is a process where several financial institutions join together to provide loans or financing to the same borrower. In this case, the borrower will receive financing from several financial institutions that are members of the syndicate. Here are several ways how syndicated financing can increase a financing portfolio:

- Risk Diversification. In syndicated financing, the risks borne by each financial institution are more diversified. Therefore, the risk borne by each financial institution will be lower than if the financial institution provided loans individually. Risk diversification can enable financial institutions to provide financing to borrowers who might not be served if the financial institution operated alone.
- Reducing the Burden of Risk. Syndicated financing can help financial institutions reduce the risk burden they bear. In syndicated financing, the risks borne by each financial institution will be more diversified. Therefore, financial institutions will have a lower risk than if they provide loans individually.
- Increasing Borrower Eligibility. In syndicated financing, the borrower will receive financing from several financial institutions that are members of the syndication. In this case, the borrower will have access to more capital and be more likely to meet the eligibility criteria. Borrowers will also be able to obtain financing on better terms because syndicated financing offers greater economies of scale.
- Increasing Market Reach. Syndicated financing can also help financial institutions to increase market reach. In this case, financial institutions will be able to offer financing to borrowers who might not be able to be served if they operated on their own. In this case, syndicated financing can help financial institutions to expand market share and increase their financing portfolio.
- Reducing Capital Expenses. Syndicated financing can help financial institutions to reduce the capital burden they bear. In syndicated financing, financial institutions will be involved in providing financing to borrowers together with other financial institutions. Therefore, the capital burden borne by each financial institution will be lower than if it provided individual loans.

Eleventh, syndicated investment in venture capital and corporate innovation. Syndicated investment in venture capital and corporate innovation is a strategy that can help investors to mitigate risks and increase potential profits. Syndication is a process where several investors join together to invest in a company. Venture capital is a form of investment in which investors provide seed capital to startup companies that are still in their early stages or are developing. Venture capital investments can help companies to develop new products, expand market reach, and improve their operational capabilities. Syndicated investments in venture capital can help reduce investment risk by sharing the burden between several investors. In addition, syndication can also help investors access greater investment opportunities than they would get if they invested alone. In terms of corporate innovation, syndicated investments can help companies to develop new technologies, expand product ranges, and increase their competitiveness in the market. Investors who join a syndicate can bring different experiences and resources, so they can help companies achieve their innovation goals. However, investors must conduct careful due diligence before joining an investment syndication. Investors must ensure that the company they are going to invest in has good business prospects, has competent management, and has a product or service that has the potential to be successful in the market. In

addition, investors must also take into account the risks and potential benefits of syndicated investments in venture capital and corporate innovation before they make investment decisions. In this case, investors can seek help from experienced financial professionals to assist them in choosing the right investment.

Twelfth, transfer of syndicated credit risk through Credit Derivate instruments and Cessie Law, namely:

- Credit Derivative Instruments. Credit derivative instruments are financial contracts used to transfer credit risk from one party to another. In the context of syndication, banks acting as lenders can use credit derivative instruments to reduce the credit risk they have for the borrower. An example of a credit derivative instrument that can be used in syndication is a credit default swap (CDS). CDS is a contract in which the buyer (bank) pays a premium to the seller (usually an insurance institution or other bank) to protect itself from the risk of default or default by the borrower. If a default occurs, the seller will pay the buyer according to the amount agreed in the contract.
- Cessie's Law. Cessie law is a mechanism for transferring claims or receivables from one party to another party. In the context of syndication, banks that want to reduce their credit risk can use the cessie law to transfer their claim rights over the borrower to other banks or investors. The process of transferring claim rights through cessie law is usually carried out by handing over claim rights in writing or endorsement of debt securities owned by the bank to other banks or investors. In this case, the bank or investor who receives the claim rights will become the holder of the new claim rights on the debt securities.

By using credit derivative instruments or cessie law, banks participating in syndication can reduce their credit risk to the borrower. However, it should be remembered that the use of these two mechanisms must take into account the applicable rules and regulations and pay attention to the possible impact on the finances of the bank and other related parties.

Thirteenth, Syndicated Loan Agreement and Security Sharing Agreement. Syndicated Loan Agreement is an agreement between several banks or creditors to provide loans to the same borrower. Basically, credit syndication is a form of cooperation between several banks or creditors to provide large loans that are divided among them. In this agreement, the borrower promises to repay the loan and agrees to the terms and conditions set by the bank or creditor involved in the credit syndication. The Syndicated Loan Agreement contains detailed information about the loan provided, including the loan amount, interest rate, loan term, and interest and principal payments. In addition, these agreements may also include additional terms, such as security provisions and requirements for the use of loan funds. Security Sharing Agreement is an agreement between several banks or creditors involved in a credit syndication to share the security or collateral taken from the borrower as collateral for the loan provided. In this agreement, the bank or creditor agrees to share the risk in the event that the borrower cannot fulfill his obligations to repay the loan. In the Security Sharing Agreement, the bank or creditor can determine the order of priority in terms of collateral realization. This is important because if the borrower cannot repay the loan, the bank or creditor must ensure that any collateral or security taken is used effectively to repay the debt. When a borrower applies for a credit syndication, the bank or creditor will conduct a credit analysis and assess the borrower's ability to repay the loan. After agreeing to provide a loan, the bank or creditor will draw up a Syndicated Loan Agreement and Security Sharing Agreement to determine the terms and conditions for the loan.

Fourteenth, application of the Blue Ocean Strategy to syndicated financing of the Musyarakah Mutanaqishah scheme. Blue Ocean Strategy is a conceptual framework that can be applied to various business fields, including syndicated financing of the Musyarakah Mutanaqishah scheme. The following are several steps that can be taken to implement the Blue Ocean Strategy in syndicated financing of the Musyarakah Mutanaqishah scheme:

- Identify new potential markets: One of the principles of Blue Ocean Strategy is to look for new markets where there is not yet intense competition. In the Musyarakah Mutanaqishah scheme syndicated financing, new potential markets can lie in customer segments that are not reached by conventional financing products. For example, financing for micro, small and medium enterprises (MSMEs) or financing for sectors that are considered less profitable, such as the agricultural or tourism sectors.
- Innovating in products and services: In the Musyarakah Mutanaqishah syndicated financing scheme, companies can develop new products and services that are more innovative and

relevant to the new potential markets that have been identified. For example, financing products tailored to the needs of MSMEs or financing services with faster and easier processes to make things easier for customers.

- Focus on value for customers: Blue Ocean Strategy emphasizes the importance of providing value for customers. In the Musyarakah Mutanaqishah scheme syndicated financing, companies can provide added value to customers by providing consulting and assistance services to assist customers in developing their businesses.
- Determining the right marketing strategy: To introduce new products and services to potential markets, companies need to determine the right marketing strategy. For example, carrying out promotions via social media or collaborating with organizations or institutions that focus on the target sector.

In implementing the Blue Ocean Strategy in syndicated financing of the Musyarakah Mutanaqishah scheme, companies must always consider sharia compliance in all decisions and policies taken.

Fifteenth, the juridical implications of changing the status of a conventional bank to a sharia bank for syndicated credit. Changing the status of a conventional bank to a sharia bank has juridical implications for syndicated credit. Syndicated credit is credit provided by several banks jointly to the borrowing party. The juridical implications of changing the status of a conventional bank to a sharia bank for syndicated credit can be explained as follows:

- Changes in Creditors. In syndicated credit, there are usually several conventional banks as creditors. In the event that the status of a conventional bank changes to a sharia bank, the conventional bank will leave the syndicated credit, and the new sharia bank will enter as a creditor. Therefore, the parties involved in syndicated credit must renegotiate and make changes to the syndicated credit agreement to comply with changes in bank status.
- Regulatory Changes. The change in bank status from conventional to sharia will have an impact on changes to the regulations governing the bank. Islamic banks must comply with sharia banking regulations which are different from conventional banking regulations. Therefore, parties in syndicated credit must pay attention to applicable sharia banking regulations to avoid violations in the use of credit funds.
- Changes to the Credit Agreement. The change in bank status from conventional to sharia will have an impact on changes to the credit agreement. Credit contracts at conventional banks are different from credit contracts at sharia banks. Therefore, the parties to a syndicated credit must make changes to the credit agreement in accordance with sharia banking regulations.
- Changes in Creditor Obligations. Changing a bank's status from conventional to sharia will have an impact on changes in creditor obligations. Sharia banks have different obligations from conventional banks in providing credit. Therefore, parties in syndicated credit must pay attention to changes in creditor obligations that apply to sharia banks.

Sixteenth, resolving syndicated bad credit disputes internally and externally. Syndicated bad credit dispute resolution can be done internally and externally. The following is a brief explanation of these two methods: (1) Internal settlement is carried out between the bank and the syndicate members. This method is done by negotiating and mediating between the two parties to find the best solution to resolve the bad credit problem. Banks and syndicate members can hold regular meetings and discussions to discuss solutions that can be implemented to resolve bad credit. (2) External settlement can be carried out through arbitration institutions or courts. If internal resolution cannot resolve a bad credit dispute, the bank and syndicate members can submit the dispute to an arbitration institution or court to seek a more firm and binding solution. Banks and syndicate members can hire lawyers who are experts in this matter to represent them in arbitration or trial proceedings. In resolving syndicated bad credit disputes, it is important for both parties to be able to communicate well and consider solutions that benefit both parties and minimize losses. Therefore, the solutions found must be considered carefully and taken with full consideration in order to avoid larger conflicts.

Seventeenth, application of syndicated financing in sharia banking. The following are the steps for implementing syndicated financing in banking: (1) Identify financing needs: Banks that will provide syndicated financing must carry out a risk and feasibility analysis to ensure that the project or business to be financed has the potential to provide substantial profits for the borrower and bank. (2) Forming a consortium: Banks that will join in syndicated financing must form a consortium and determine the roles and responsibilities of each bank in providing loans. (3) Determination of financing structure: The

financing structure must be determined to ensure that the risks taken by each bank are in accordance with the agreed proportions. (4) Determination of terms and conditions: Terms and conditions of financing must be clearly determined, including loan amount, term, interest rate, collateral, and so on. (5) Risk assessment: Banks involved in syndicated financing must carry out regular risk assessments and monitor the use of funds by borrowers. (6) Completion of financing: Once all requirements are met, funds will be distributed to the borrower and financing will begin. (7) Supervision: Banks involved in syndicated financing must continuously monitor the use of funds by borrowers and take action if problems or undesirable risks occur.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded as follows:

- The number of research publications regarding Syndication in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions during the period 2011 to 2022 shows a significant increase from year to year. The total number of publications is 41 research articles, which come from national journals indexed by Sinta.
- The affiliate/institution that publishes the most research results is Lex Et Societatis, with 3 articles.
- In the mapping visualization using VOSviewer, research developments regarding Syndication in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions are divided into 9 clusters and 140 topic items. Cluster 1 consists of 27 topics, cluster 2 consists of 20 topics, cluster 3 consists of 19 topics, cluster 4 consists of 19 topics, cluster 5 consists of 19 topics, cluster 6 consists of 11 topics, cluster 7 consists of 10 topics, cluster 8 consists of 8 topics, and cluster 9 consists of 7 topics.
- Based on a literature review, there are 17 Problems in Credit Syndication in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

It is recommended that further research use a larger data sample, so that it can explain a broader research mapping, considering the limitations of the data sample in this study and can add a longer research data time span so that the following research results can be obtained:

- It is hoped that the mapping results will show a higher and broader level of generalization.
- the literature review study can be explained in a more complex way.

REFERENCES

- [Sahni, S.](#) and [Singh Kaurav, R.P.](#) (2023), "What? Why? When? How? Where? of Technology-Based Bibliometric Review", [Rana, S., Singh, J. and Kathuria, S.](#) (Ed.) *Advancing Methodologies of Conducting Literature Review in Management Domain (Review of Management Literature, Vol. 2)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 79-101. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2754-586520230000002005>
- [Anlesinya, A.](#) and [Dadzie, S.A.](#) (2023), "Technology and the Conduct of Bibliometric Literature Reviews in Management: The Software Tools, Benefits, and Challenges", [Rana, S., Singh, J. and Kathuria, S.](#) (Ed.) *Advancing Methodologies of Conducting Literature Review in Management Domain (Review of Management Literature, Vol. 2)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 57-78. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2754-586520230000002004>
- [Mulet-Forteza, C., Genovart-Balaguer, J. and Horrach-Rosselló, P.](#) (2022), "Bibliometric Studies in the Hospitality and Tourism Field: A Guide for Researchers", [Okumus, F., Rasoolimanesh, S.M. and Jahani, S.](#) (Ed.) *Contemporary Research Methods in Hospitality and Tourism*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 55-76. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-80117-546-320221005>
- [Ülker, P., Ülker, M. and Karamustafa, K.](#) (2023), "Bibliometric analysis of bibliometric studies in the field of tourism and hospitality", *Journal of Hospitality and Tourism Insights*, Vol. 6 No. 2, pp. 797-818. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JHTI-10-2021-0291>

- [Song, Y.](#) and [Cao, J.](#) (2022), "An ARIMA-based study of bibliometric index prediction", *Aslib Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 74 No. 1, pp. 94-109. <https://doi.org/10.1108/AJIM-03-2021-0072>
- [Akhil, M.P.](#) (2022), "Employing Bibliometric Analysis to Identify Emerging Technologies in the Insurance Industry", [Sood, K.](#), [Balusamy, B.](#), [Grima, S.](#) and [Marano, P.](#) (Ed.) *Big Data Analytics in the Insurance Market (Emerald Studies in Finance, Insurance, and Risk Management)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 207-220. <https://doi.org/10.1108/978-1-80262-637-720221011>
- [Ahuja, D.](#), [Bhardwaj, P.](#) and [Madan, P.](#) (2023), "Money Laundering: A Bibliometric Review of Three Decades from 1990 to 2021", [Tyagi, P.](#), [Grima, S.](#), [Sood, K.](#), [Balamurugan, B.](#), [Özen, E.](#) and [Eleftherios, T.](#) (Ed.) *Smart Analytics, Artificial Intelligence and Sustainable Performance Management in a Global Digitalised Economy (Contemporary Studies in Economic and Financial Analysis, Vol. 110B)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 55-72. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1569-37592023000110B003>
- [Güngör Göksu, G.](#) (2023), "A retrospective overview of the Journal of Public Budgeting, Accounting and Financial Management using bibliometric analysis", *Journal of Public Budgeting, Accounting & Financial Management*, Vol. 35 No. 2, pp. 264-295. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPBAFM-04-2022-0061>
- [Wani, J.A.](#), [Ganaie, S.A.](#) and [Rehman, I.U.](#) (2023), "Mapping research output on library and information science research domain in South Africa: a bibliometric visualisation", *Information Discovery and Delivery*, Vol. 51 No. 2, pp. 194-212. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IDD-10-2021-0115>
- [Ralph, A.](#) and [Arora, A.](#) (2023), "A bibliometric study of reference literature on youth unemployment", *Journal of Enterprising Communities: People and Places in the Global Economy*, Vol. 17 No. 6, pp. 1338-1367. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JEC-04-2022-0062>
- [Ryan, J.C.](#) (2021), "Retaining, resigning and firing: bibliometrics as a people analytics tool for examining research performance outcomes and faculty turnover", *Personnel Review*, Vol. 50 No. 5, pp. 1316-1335. <https://doi.org/10.1108/PR-12-2019-0676>
- [Mokhtari, H.](#), [Barkhan, S.](#), [Haseli, D.](#) and [Saber, M.K.](#) (2021), "A bibliometric analysis and visualization of the Journal of Documentation: 1945–2018", *Journal of Documentation*, Vol. 77 No. 1, pp. 69-92. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JD-08-2019-0165>
- [Farooq, R.](#) (2024), "A review of knowledge management research in the past three decades: a bibliometric analysis", *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, Vol. 54 No. 2, pp. 339-378. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-08-2021-0169>
- [Siddique, N.](#), [Ur Rehman, S.](#), [Ahmad, S.](#), [Abbas, A.](#) and [Khan, M.A.](#) (2023), "Library and information science research in the Arab World: a bibliometric analysis 1951–2021", *Global Knowledge, Memory and Communication*, Vol. 72 No. 1/2, pp. 138-159. <https://doi.org/10.1108/GKMC-06-2021-0103>
- [Islam, M.A.](#) and [Widen, G.](#) (2023), "Bibliometric analysis of the VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems: 2000–2020", *VINE Journal of Information and Knowledge Management Systems*, Vol. 53 No. 3, pp. 467-490. <https://doi.org/10.1108/VJIKMS-07-2020-0126>
- [Perannagari, K.T.](#) and [Gupta, S.](#) (2022), "Mapping the Intellectual Structure of Artificial Neural Network Research in Business Domain: A Retrospective Overview Using Bibliometric Review", [Rana, S.](#), [Sakshi](#) and [Singh, J.](#) (Ed.) *Exploring the Latest Trends in Management*

Literature (Review of Management Literature, Vol. 1), Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 35-59. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2754-586520220000001003>

[Davidescu, A.A.](#), [Hapau, R.G.](#) and [Manta, E.M.](#) (2022), "Impact of Crises on Capital Market Volatility: A Bibliometric Analysis", [Grima, S.](#), [Özen, E.](#) and [Boz, H.](#) (Ed.) *The New Digital Era: Other Emerging Risks and Opportunities (Contemporary Studies in Economic and Financial Analysis, Vol. 109B)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 21-53. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S1569-37592022000109B003>

[Ali, Q.](#), [Parveen, S.](#), [Aspiranti, T.](#), [Nurhayati, N.](#) and [Rusgianto, S.](#) (2023), "Barriers to the adoption of Islamic banking: a bibliometric analysis", *International Journal of Ethics and Systems*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IJOES-01-2023-0001>

[Kumar, S.](#), [Goyal, P.](#), [Kumar, V.](#) and [Vandana.](#) (2022), "Cultural Diversity in Tourism: A Bibliometric Analysis of 33 Years (1988–2021)", [Rana, S.](#), [Sakshi](#) and [Singh, J.](#) (Ed.) *Exploring the Latest Trends in Management Literature (Review of Management Literature, Vol. 1)*, Emerald Publishing Limited, Leeds, pp. 147-168. <https://doi.org/10.1108/S2754-586520220000001008>

[Chhtrapati, D.](#), [Trivedi, D.](#), [Chaudhari, S.P.](#), [Sharma, A.](#) and [Bhatt, A.](#) (2024), "Global research performance on social media security: a bibliometric visualization analysis", *Information Discovery and Delivery*, Vol. 52 No. 1, pp. 101-113. <https://doi.org/10.1108/IDD-04-2022-0029>